

Bridging the Mentoring Gap: Rethinking School Placement Support in Initial Teacher Education in Ireland.

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School placement is a vital component of initial teacher education where student teachers integrate theoretical knowledge with practical application in diverse primary educational contexts. While school placement plays a significant role in shaping professional teacher identity and resilience, limited structured mentoring supports are available to student teachers, potentially impacting their professional development and mental well-being. This paper explores the existing roles of *treoraithe* (co-operating teachers) and Higher Education Institution (HEI)-appointed school placement tutors, highlighting the need to provide more sustained mentoring. Drawing on international models, it argues that carefully designed, HEI-led mentoring frameworks could help address this problem of practice. Such frameworks would align with the theoretical and reflective dimensions of ITE, foster student teachers' professional growth and resilience, and alleviate some of the pressures on *treoraithe*. Furthermore, enhanced HEI-led mentoring has the potential to strengthen HEI / school partnerships and to support student teachers' emerging professional identities. The paper concludes by outlining the contours of a structured HEI-led mentoring model and by signalling implications for policy, practice and research. It argues that re-imagining the role of school placement tutors as longer-term mentors represents a promising way to bridge the current gap between assessment-focused support and the broader demands of learning to teach.

Keywords: Initial Teacher Education; Student Teachers; Teacher Identity; School Placement; Mentoring

Highlights

- School placement is a highly formative element of initial teacher education which can present significant personal and professional challenges for student teachers.
- While *treoraithe* mentor student teachers during school placement, students are assessed by HEI-appointed school placement tutors and contact with them is limited and episodic.
- The role of school placement tutors could be reimagined to incorporate sustained mentoring to support the development of student teachers' professional identity and resilience.

Introduction

Initial teacher education (ITE) is an unusual educational process whereby the act of educating student teachers becomes both the method and the subject matter of study. Within ITE, school placement refers to the period during which student teachers work in school settings and have opportunities to “integrate educational theory and practice in a variety of teaching situations and school contexts” (Teaching Council, 2021, p. 4). Waldron describes this as “the most powerful site of integration for student learning” (2014, p. 7), underscoring the centrality of school placement in professional formation. During placement, student teachers are assessed by HEI-appointed placement tutors on their planning and preparation, and teaching and learning, all under the umbrella of professionalism. Feldon (2007) notes that newly-qualified teachers can be overwhelmed by the “simultaneous activity” (p. 123) of classroom life. This is especially true for student teachers, who experience what might be termed a ‘double cognitive load’: they must draw on their studies while planning and preparing to meet the diverse needs of their classes, all while being observed and assessed. Student teachers must therefore be mindful of pupils’ cognitive load at the same time as they strive to integrate their own theoretical and practical learning.

This paper, with its focus on professional learning and teacher education, argues that a significant gap exists within primary school placement: the lack of sustained, structured mentoring by HEI-based teacher educators. While student teachers receive day-to-day support from *treoraithe*, their contact with HEI placement tutors is typically limited to one or two visits per placement block. Drawing on literature, international examples and the author’s positionality, the paper makes a case for enhanced HEI-led mentoring to better support student teachers’ development, resilience and emerging professional identities.

Initial Teacher Education and School Placement in Ireland

Céim: Standards for Initial Teacher Education (Teaching Council, 2020) is the starting point on the Teaching Council’s continuum of teacher education. *Céim* outlines both programme standards and graduate teacher standards that ITE providers must meet for the accredited preparation of primary and post-primary teachers in Ireland. The term ‘school placement’ has replaced ‘teaching practice’, thereby “emphasising the need for [student teachers] to gain an understanding and experience of the wider culture and practices in a school” (Hall et al., 2018, p. 21). A more broadly based whole-school experience is therefore expected beyond direct teaching alone. While *Céim* applies to both sectors, this paper addresses school placement in a primary ITE context.

Tutoring versus Mentoring

Orland-Barak (2016) distinguishes between tutors, who provide academic assistance within a specific subject area, and mentors, who take a broader role in offering feedback, advice and guidance. The Teaching Council defines a placement tutor as “a person engaged by a HEI to support and mentor [student teachers] and evaluate their practice while on placement” (2021, p. 4). Placement tutors are typically teacher-educators working within HEIs or externally-recruited teachers and school leaders with substantial professional experience. The tutor’s role in mentoring student teachers is both subtle and distinct from that of the *treoraí* because of its evaluative dimension. Hall et al. (2017) suggest that *treoraithe* tend to have strengths around the “what” and “how” of practice, while HEI tutors more often address the “why” (p. 52). Placement tutors liaise with *treoraithe* about student teachers’ progress, but their formal assessment is based on a small number of visits, focussed observation and scrutiny of planning and preparation. The mentoring element of a tutor’s visit occurs after the observation and within tight time constraints. Depending on institutional arrangements, placement tutors may not be known to student teachers prior to visiting their classrooms. In many cases, therefore, student teachers’ only direct contact with their HEI during placement is through one or two brief tutor visits. In the Irish context, placement tutors occupy a hybrid position: they are engaged to support and assess student teachers, while the *treoraí* is positioned as the primary mentor. Many placement tutors undoubtedly enact mentoring practices, but the time-limited nature of school visits means this support is episodic rather than sustained.

The Union of Students in Ireland’s *Student Teacher Placement Survey* highlights that 96% of respondents found placement to be “highly stressful” (USI, 2018, p. 5). Sources of stress included the volume of planning and preparation and the financial burden associated with placement. This report also emphasises the impact of placement on student teachers’ mental health and calls for greater structural support. Within this landscape, HEI-based teacher educators could play more of a continuous mentoring role alongside assessment responsibilities.

Student Teacher Professional Identity

Professional identity has been described as a “personal framework that guides one’s perceptions, interpretations, and actions in job-embedded situations” (Richter, 2021, p. 21). McKeon and Harrison define it as a “socially and culturally constructed ‘self’ formed through a life’s experiences and through communication about these experiences” (2010, p. 27).

Wenger (1998) similarly emphasises identity as an evolving construct shaped through participation in communities of practice. For student teachers, school placement is one of the most significant sites in which professional identity begins to form.

Upon entering ITE, student teachers are typically drawn from the upper echelons of educational attainment within their peer groups. To qualify as primary teachers in Ireland, they must complete either a four-year Bachelor of Education (BEd) or a two-year Professional Master of Education (Primary) (PMEP). Both routes are academically demanding and place a strong emphasis on practicum, as evidenced in *Céim*'s school placement requirements. Within placement settings, student teachers' professional identities are shaped as they move "to the other side of the desk" (Lortie, 1975) and negotiate how they wish to be seen by pupils, colleagues, parents and placement tutors as "good teachers" (MacDonald, 1996).

This process is challenging. In addition to the stressors identified by USI (2018), the literature highlights other difficulties faced by student teachers, including developing self-efficacy (Kitching, Morgan and O'Leary, 2009), mastering classroom management (Gibbs and Miller, 2014) and exercising professional judgement in complex situations (Castro, Kelly and Shih, 2010). Cochran-Smith (2005) argues that the intensity of ITE programmes and the motivation required to succeed are key drivers in the development of teacher identity. Student teachers must navigate demanding expectations while still constructing a sense of who they are, and who they want to become, as professionals.

Resilience is closely intertwined with this identity work. Richardson et al. (1990) define resilience as "the process of coping with disruptive, stressful, or challenging life events in a way that provides the individual with additional protective and coping skills" (p. 34). On school placement, student teachers' resilience shapes how they respond to challenges; this, in turn, affects their classroom effectiveness, self-efficacy and stress levels (Quintilliani, 2011). Resilient student teachers also contribute to building resilience in their pupils through encouragement, high expectations and opportunities to develop strengths.

Taken together, these perspectives suggest that identity formation and resilience are mutually reinforcing. A mentoring model that attends only to the technical aspects of planning and teaching is unlikely to be sufficient. Instead, student teachers need support to reflect on their experiences, to make sense of tensions and setbacks, and to see themselves as capable professionals who can grow through challenge.

Making the Case for HEI-led School Placement Mentoring

Having outlined the purpose and challenges of school placement, the roles of key actors and the importance of identity and resilience, this section sets out why enhanced HEI-led mentoring should be considered and why its absence is identified here as a problem of practice in ITE.

The argument is shaped by the author's positionality as a primary teacher and principal whose professional identity is now also evolving as a teacher educator. Observing ITE from both sides of the HEI / school relationship foregrounds the complexity of placement and the unevenness of mentoring provision. While *treoraithe* support student teachers daily, their own professional demands, identities and resilience shape the mentoring they can offer. They are rightly focused on the class of children for whom they hold primary responsibility. Their practice does not always align neatly with HEI expectations or assessment criteria, which can place student teachers in the middle of conflicting messages.

In this context, HEI placement tutors occupy a unique vantage point. Through their involvement in programme design, research and assessment, they hold a broader overview of ITE aims, Teaching Council standards and school placement requirements. They are therefore well-positioned to offer mentoring that supports student teachers' reflective practice, identity formation and resilience, in addition to providing feedback on planning and teaching. At present, however, the episodic nature of tutor visits means this potential is only partially realised.

International examples point towards the feasibility of more structured HEI-led mentoring. In Singapore and the Netherlands, university-based teacher-educators play sustained roles in schools alongside school-based mentors (Tan, Lie and Low, 2012; van Velzen and van der Klink, 2014). These systems suggest that context-sensitive combinations of school- and HEI-led mentoring can strengthen the bridge between theory and practice.

A possible model in the Irish context would see each student teacher assigned an HEI-based mentor who works with them across multiple placement blocks. This mentor would:

- meet student teachers, individually or in small groups, before placement to explore expectations, concerns and goals;
- maintain contact during placement through scheduled online or in-person check-ins;
- facilitate structured reflective conversations after tutor visits that go beyond lesson evaluation to include identity, resilience and professional decision-making; and
- act as a consistent point of contact across the programme, complementing the day-to-day guidance of *treoraithe*.

Such a model would have resource implications, particularly in relation to staffing and workload. However, it also carries clear implications for policy, practice and research:

- National frameworks, including Teaching Council standards and Department of Education resourcing, could explicitly recognise and support HEI-led mentoring as part of ITE staffing structures.
- HEIs and schools could co-design mentoring arrangements that clarify complementary roles for *treoraithe* and HEI mentors, reducing role confusion and supporting more coherent messages for student teachers.
- Pilot HEI-led mentoring initiatives could be evaluated to examine their impact on student teacher identity, resilience and placement experiences, with particular attention to diverse cohorts of students and school contexts.

While HEI-led mentoring is not a panacea for the current lack of mentoring-focused professional learning for *treoraithe*, it offers one concrete avenue for addressing a clear gap in current provision.

Conclusion

In the Irish context, school placement is rightly positioned at the heart of initial teacher education, yet the mentoring structures that surround it remain uneven and, in many cases, under-developed. *Treoraithe* carry significant responsibility for supporting student teachers but may not have access to sustained mentoring-specific professional learning. HEI placement tutors, meanwhile, often have the expertise and programme-level perspective to mentor student teachers more holistically, yet their institutional role is frequently limited to episodic assessment visits.

By drawing on national policy, international examples and literature on professional identity and resilience, this paper has made the case for re-imagining school placement tutors' roles to include sustained HEI-led mentoring. A structured model in which each student teacher is paired with an HEI mentor across multiple placements could bolster identity development, strengthen resilience, share the mentoring load with *treoraithe*, and deepen HEI-school partnerships.

The discussion has highlighted several implications. For policy, there is a need to consider how national standards and funding mechanisms can support HEI-led mentoring as part of core ITE provision. For practice, HEIs and schools could collaborate to design context-sensitive mentoring arrangements that acknowledge the differing needs of

undergraduate and postgraduate student teachers and the realities of diverse school settings. For research, there is a clear opportunity to examine how HEI-led mentoring models operate in practice and what they mean for student teachers' experiences, professional identities and longer-term career trajectories.

Ultimately, if school placement is to remain the “most powerful site of integration for student learning” (Waldron, 2014, p. 7), then the mentoring that accompanies it deserves equal attention. Strengthening HEI-led mentoring is one promising step towards ensuring that student teachers are not only assessed, but also meaningfully supported, as they learn to teach.

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